

**Primary and secondary waste in (bio)catalysis: What matters is not what is produced, but
what permanently remains!**

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

HIGHLIGHTS

- (Bio)catalytic reactions generate waste, solvents and wastewater, which are “Primary Waste”.
- Traditional environmental mass-metrics focus on those “Primary Waste”.
- “Primary Waste” is treated in industry before released, generating CO₂ as “Secondary Waste”.
- Environmental metrics based on “Primary Waste” show discrepancy with the CO₂ formed.
- An assessment of the CO₂ produced may become useful to compare processes.

ABSTRACT

(Bio)catalysis create waste, composed of wastewater and an organic fraction. Different metrics are used for the environmental impact of processes, being E-Factor and PMI the prominent ones. These metrics are typically applied to the wastewater and the organic fraction, which is the process “Primary Waste”. However, “Primary Waste” is industrially treated before released to the environment. When treating “Primary Waste”, CO₂ is generated, from the Wastewater Treatment Plant and from the organic fraction incineration. That CO₂, the “Secondary Waste”, remains in the planet, and thus should be the target for environmental assessments. When E-Factor and PMI from “Primary Waste” are compared to produced CO₂, results mismatch, because the CO₂ depends on the proportion wastewater/organic fraction, since incineration leads to higher CO₂ production than wastewater treatment. Future options are incorporating renewable energy and biogenic solvents (neutral carbon), and developing (new) wastewater treatment strategies, to deliver pure(r) water effluents to the environment.

Key-words: Biocatalysis; E-Factor; C-Factor; CO₂ production; Green Chemistry; Sustainable Chemistry.

1. Measuring the environmental impact of a (bio)catalytic reaction.

Modern industrial (bio)catalytic reactions must comply with two important objectives, namely the economic efficiency of the process – assuring its ultimate marketability –, and the environmental friendliness of the proposed strategy. Actions devoted to process intensification may pave the way for an optimized use of resources by establishing systems at high substrate loadings, with adequate reactor set-up, and with robust biocatalysts, and therefore can crucially contribute to reach these two goals simultaneously [1-6,7*]. The tremendous development in biocatalysis over the last decades has led to many industrial enzymatic applications, comprising not only the production of highly valuable building blocks for pharmaceuticals and fine chemicals – the traditional niche of enzyme catalysis –, but also an increasing number of bulk and biorefinery-based applications from which biocatalysis can be an key-enabling technology [8,9].

Biocatalysis has been traditionally placed within the Green Chemistry postulates by providing qualitative statements (e.g. “enzymes are renewable and green *per se*”). Yet, over the last decades a more critical perception requires the incorporation of quantitative environmental metrics to substantiate its greenness [1,2,10,11]. From the different metrics that can be used to assess the environmental (un)friendliness of a process, the Sheldon’s E-factor (kilograms of waste by kilogram of product) is possibly the most widely employed one, due to its intuitiveness and straightforward use [12-15,16**]. The use of Process Mass Intensity (PMI), however, has been prioritized for the pharmaceutical industry [17], although in any case the conversion from the E-Factor to PMI results trivial ($PMI = E\text{-Factor} + 1$), and both metrics can be used simultaneously to assess waste production and resource optimization. It must be noted that the use of both PMI or E-factor is often restricted to the synthetic process as such, the so-called “gate-to-gate” approach. For the holistic assessment, the environmental impact of the pre-steps related to the production of chemicals and solvents – whether biogenic or petrochemical –, together with their transportation to the chemical plant, etc., must also be addressed, through Life-Cycle-

Assessments (LCA) [2,12,18], which account on the wastes associated to the synthesis of substrates, enzymes, and solvents. Furthermore, their hazardousness and biodegradability must be necessarily considered if a holistic environmental assessment is to be made [19].

Despite its wide use to assess the process greenness, limitations of the E-Factor have been pinpointed as well. Among them, the need of assigning a *quality value* to the wastes was tackled by the early-on incorporation of the “environmental quotient”, which would assign some weights to the wastes, depending on their hazardousness [12,16**]. Likewise, the incorporation of the environmental impact of the energy by the E⁺-Factor was proposed recently [20], to incorporate the CO₂ formation that electricity of the chemical plant may produce. Despite these limitations, however, the E-Factor is increasingly being used in (bio)catalytic applications, and many publications incorporate nowadays the environmental assessment when developing novel enzymatic routes [21-33,34*,35**,36*,37*].

Undoubtedly, measuring the wastes of a reaction is crucial to tackle sustainability, and it is important that such analyses can be conducted more systematically in early research steps of new syntheses, to assure that corrective actions are timely taken. However, one must keep in mind that industrial waste effluents are treated before reaching the environment. Admittedly, there are accidental spills from time to time, and wastes that may be inadequately and/or incompletely treated, but the majority of the produced industrial waste is subjected to increasingly stricter regulations. In that respect, the significance of conducting environmental assessments with emphasis on the “Primary Waste” results questionable, if they will disappear *before* reaching the environment. On that basis, this article tries to (constructively) discuss alternatives to environmentally assess the industrial waste from chemical processes, with a focus on the “Secondary Waste”.

2. Primary and Secondary waste: What matters is what reaches and remains in the planet.

Any biocatalytic process consists of two main sub-units, the upstream part, where the enzymatic biotransformation takes place, and the downstream part, where the product is purified to reach *on-spec* market conditions (Figure 1) [2,38]. The overall process needs the supply of chemicals (e.g. reagents), solvents and water, as well as energy to keep running all facilities and the reactor. The upstream sub-unit can be set-up in aqueous media (eventually, with the aid of a miscible cosolvent, such as DMSO, *isopropanol*, *tert*-butanol, acetone, etc.), or in non-conventional media, that is, in the absence of bulk water, and using organic (neoteric) solvents, gases, solvent-free, etc. Combinations thereof (e.g. biphasic systems) can be considered as well [6]. Once the product is formed, several downstream steps are established. In some cases, a simple product precipitation and washing may be sufficient, but in other cases, in particular when highly purified pharma-quality products are made, several downstream steps are needed to reach the required purity threshold [2].

Figure 1. Overall picture of an industrial (bio)catalytic process, comprising the upstream and downstream, and the different waste types that are formed, and their treatment.

The two (bio)catalytic sub-units generate waste, mostly in the form of an aqueous fraction, which will be sent to the Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP), and an organic fraction, which pools all spent (impure) solvents and will be sent to incineration. These effluents can be regarded as “Primary Waste”. Since such collected waste is treated before releasing them to the environment, it will not stay in the planet (except, as stated above, if accidents occur, or an inadequate waste treatment is conducted).

The “Primary Waste” is the one that is usually quantified when mass-metrics are used. However, would that assessment be relevant, if that “Primary Waste” disappears when treated? Would it not be more meaningful to focus on the “Secondary Waste” that is generated upon the treatment of the “Primary Waste”. The impact when treating those wastes results in the generation of CO₂, either from the WWTP – energy consumption –, or from the incineration unit

(which, apart from CO₂, will also generate some energy that can be recycled in the chemical plant). Furthermore, the CO₂ produced from the invested energy to run the (bio)catalytic unit must be added to that “Secondary Waste” too (Figure 1).

The produced CO₂ as remaining “Secondary Waste” is the permanent waste that the chemical process is generating. The value – estimated as kg CO₂ · kg Product⁻¹ –, was coined as the “C-Factor” some decades ago [39*], and it is commonly assessed in LCA as one of the Impact Factors (Global Warming Potential) [2]. More recently, the Gallou group at Novartis has proposed the term TCR, “Total Carbon Dioxide Release”, and has estimated the average (industrial) values of CO₂ production related to different wastewater treatment options and to the incineration units [40,41**]. Importantly, the provision of such estimative-but-realistic industrial values for the CO₂ production has stimulated several groups to use the TCR to assess the environmental impact of (bio)catalytic processes [2,18,19,34*,42*,43**]. In fact, with these tools in hand, one can compare waste formation of different processes, as everything is converted to the same “currency”, that is, the kilograms of CO₂ generated when one kilogram of product is formed. Furthermore, the approach allows waste allocation among sub-units, and thus broader boundaries for the assessment, to include the transportation impact or the CO₂ formation during the substrate or enzyme production, can be included in further studies, and become comparable to other systems. Likewise, it may stimulate research in carbon sequestration, to avoid that the final wastes are released to the environment in the form of CO₂ [44].

3. How do E-Factor and PMI of Primary Waste (mis)match with CO₂ production as Secondary Waste?

Once that the overall (simplified) picture of waste formation and treatment is considered – separating the impact of Primary and Secondary Waste (Figure 1) –, the next question would be whether the usually measured E-Factor and PMI on “Primary Waste” can match with the ultimate

waste that remains in the planet (the ones for which we should worry about!). To that end, a generic (bio)catalytic reaction was considered at different substrate loadings (25-150 g substrate L⁻¹), either in aqueous media or in an organic solvent (non-conventional). Estimations for the complete E-Factor (cEF, including water and solvents), the PMI (resources + product) were provided, together with the TCR values based on the Novartis metrics [40,41**]. Three scenarios for TCR were proposed for the (bio)catalytic process: i) reaction in an organic solvent, which is incinerated; ii) reaction in water, with wastewater that must be incinerated (worst case for water); iii) reaction in water, with a wastewater that can be mildly treated in the WWTP. To simplify, only the upstream sub-unit, and a single use of water or solvents, were considered at this point (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Environmental impact of the upstream sub-unit of a generic (bio)catalytic reaction at different substrate loadings (25-150 g L⁻¹), assuming 100 % yield and single use of solvents and water. Metrics provided: cEF, PMI, and CO₂ production during waste treatment.

The first conclusion from Figure 2 is that E-Factor and PMI clearly indicate that process intensification (higher substrate loadings) is crucial to achieve decent environmental impacts, as stated elsewhere [1,2,6,7*,10,14,42*]. Thus, values of E-Factor or PMI for a biotransformation at 100 g L⁻¹ would be in the range of 10, while a 4-fold higher impact is expected at 25 g L⁻¹. Thus, the use of these widely used metrics helps determine how the best conditions for the overall process may be, create awareness of the waste produced, and provide hints on how to improve the sustainability.

However, large discrepancies are always observed when cEF and PMI are compared with the CO₂ production of *the same* (bio)catalytic process. In fact, *the same* biotransformation can lead to a rather negligible environmental impact – when mild WWTP can be assured –, or to a significant one when a single use of the organic media is made, and then incinerated. As an example, for a biotransformation at 100 g substrate L⁻¹, the TCR of a process in aqueous conditions would range from 6.3 kg CO₂ (worst case, incineration) to 0.73 (best case), while the same process in an organic media would lead to 23 kg CO₂. E-Factor and PMI of that process, on the other hand, would stay invariably in the range of 10-11. The CO₂ impact of the water treatment depends on the recalcitrance of the effluent. While in some cases a mild treatment can be accepted (according to regulations related to the biodegradability of the effluent [41**]), in other cases water incineration is necessary. In between, other environmental impacts may be considered, where some pre-treatment units are set to remove hazardous by-products or impurities, to enable the final WWTP [41**,42*,43**]. Thus, despite issues addressed to substrate immiscibility in aqueous media [45], water is attracting increasing interest in organic synthesis, in particular with the aid of surfactants that can improve process efficiency [13,46**,47]. Moreover, opportunities for biocatalysis may arise here, if impurities could be enzymatically removed from the wastewater effluent [48], to make it acceptable for the mild WWTP with reduced CO₂ generation.

With respect to solvents, their incineration makes them less environmentally attractive, often accounting for a significant proportion of the environmental burden of a process (Figure 2) [12,16**,18,49,50]. The set-up of solvent recycling strategies is an obvious path to follow, albeit severe industrial regulations may somewhat hamper these initiatives [43**,51]. Moreover, the incorporation of bio-based solvents may ameliorate, at least in part, the CO₂ impact, since a proportion of the released gases would become neutral.

The assessment of the “Secondary Waste” can also be conducted for the downstream sub-unit, and it enables the rapid and fair comparison among proposed systems (as everything is measured in the same “currency”). Figure 3 depicts the downstream of a generic (bio)catalytic reaction at 100 g substrate L⁻¹, performed either in water or in CPME as (potential) bio-based solvent [35**,52]. The downstream of the aqueous solution can be made through extraction with ethyl acetate (2X), or by water distillation. For the biotransformation in CPME, a solvent distillation recovery was considered. For comparison, different scenarios ranging from full to zero solvent recovery were modelled (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Downstream of a generic (bio)catalytic reaction at 100 g L^{-1} , performed either in water or in CPME, assuming: i) water distillation; ii) water extraction with ethyl acetate (2X); iii) distillation to recover CPME. Scenarios involving full to zero solvent recovery were modelled. Distillation values were determined based on physical-chemical parameters of water, ethyl acetate and CPME, and a 30% extra was added to the final value to assume deviations from the ideal behaviour.

The distillation of organic solvents, either ethyl acetate (extractive phase) or CPME (reactive phase) leads, as expected, to reduced CO_2 formation when compared with the direct water distillation, due to their different heat capacity. It must be noted, though, that industrial distillations may become technically complex [53], and only qualitative estimations can be given at this point. Nevertheless, the distillation impact appears less significant than solvent losses, which are ultimately mineralized and converted to CO_2 (Figure 3). Thus, even reduced solvent losses (10 % per cycle) seem to surpass the environmental impact of the distillation. Clearly, the adequate handling of organic solvents, preferably with very high recovery and reuse, appears mandatory to reach acceptable environmental figures in future (bio)catalytic industrial processes. In any case, the key message is that the CO_2 impact – the “Secondary Waste” – may become a very useful tool to benchmark reactions, both up- and down-stream, and to provide meaningful data on the actual impact of chemical processes.

Finally, some considerations should be made on the origin of the solvents and the energy. Apart from developing intensified processes that can make the best possible use of resources, employing biogenic solvents may decrease the CO_2 impact, by incorporating neutral carbon to the TCR. On the other hand, the environmental impact created by the electricity is improving over the years. While some time ago the impact (taking Europe as example) was estimated in the range of $\sim 400 \text{ g CO}_2 \cdot \text{kWh}^{-1}$ [20], current EU estimations are in the range of $\sim 240 \text{ g CO}_2 \cdot \text{kWh}^{-1}$ [54], with

a descendent prognosis over the next years, upon the penetration of more renewable energy in the electrical grid [55*,56]. Actually, estimations for hydropower energy (e.g. the Norway case) are in the range of $\sim 40 \text{ g CO}_2 \cdot \text{kWh}^{-1}$ [57]. Therefore, the incorporation of low-carbon electricity in the chemical plants, together with the use of (neutral) biogenic solvents, may provide important future improvements in the generation of “Secondary Waste” in chemical industry.

Concluding remarks

(Bio)catalytic processes generate “Primary Waste” in the form of wastewater and pooled organic fractions. Process intensification leads to an improved resource use and thus to more economic and environment-friendly strategies. Traditional measurements for the environmental metrics rely on mass metrics (e.g. the E-Factor and PMI) which are based on that “Primary Waste”. However, except for accidents and/or negligent waste treatment, the generated “Primary Waste” is handled in industry before being released to the environment. During that treatment, “Secondary Waste” is created in the form of CO_2 (from WWTP and incineration units). Such “Secondary Waste” reaches and remains in the planet, and therefore should be the target for improving the environmental impact of chemical processes. Furthermore, the use of a common “currency”, namely $\text{kg CO}_2 \cdot \text{kg Product}^{-1}$ enables the fair comparison of sub-units and processes. Several options can be proposed to ameliorate the “Secondary Waste” formation: i) introduction of renewable energy in the electric grid; ii) use of biogenic solvents that are based on neutral carbon (provided that their own production may be environment-friendly as well); iii) research on wastewater treatment to develop even milder and optimized strategies for the waste effluent management, to deliver improved and pure(r) water effluents to our environment. What ultimately matters is the “Secondary Waste” because it remains in our Planet!

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